

Kanak—a new mid-early duration rice variety

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Kanak (BK773-10), a high-yielding rice variety, was evolved by the pedigree method following hybridization of Chambal and Annapurna at ARS (Rajasthan Agricultural University), Kota. In coordinated trials conducted from 1988 to 1991 at 41 locations, Kanak yielded 7.2% higher than national check Ratna. In state trials conducted for 7 y, Kanak gave a mean yield of 5.4 t ha⁻¹; compared with that of Ratna, the increase in yield was 15.2%. In five districts of Rajasthan—Kota, Bundi, Baran, Sriganganagar, and Udaipur—Kanak showed a yield improvement of 21% in 375 mini kit demonstrations (Table 1).

The effect of seedling age on grain yield of different varieties (including Kanak) was also studied in 1997-98. Results revealed that 25-d-old seedlings gave the maximum grain yield, with Kanak being first in rank among the varieties (Table 2). Likewise, response to N (up to 120 kg ha⁻¹) was also studied in 1999-2000. Results showed a maximum grain

Table 1. Yield performance of Kanak in different trials.

Variety	Mean grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Yield increase over check (%)
<i>Coordinated trials, 1988-91, 41 locations</i>		
Kanak	5.0	
Ratna (check)	4.7	7.2
<i>State trials, 1985-91</i>		
Kanak	5.4	
Ratna (check)	4.7	15.2
<i>Mini kit demonstrations, 1993, 375 locations</i>		
Kanak	5.6	
Ratna (check)	4.6	21.0
<i>Grand mean</i>		
Kanak	5.4	
Ratna (check)	4.7	14.5

Table 2. Effect of seedling age on grain yield of rice varieties.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Mean
	1997	1998	
<i>Seedling age (d)</i>			
25	5.3	5.2	5.3
32	4.7	4.7	4.7
39	4.0	4.4	4.2
46	3.8	3.9	3.8
CD (P = 0.05)	0.18	0.28	
CV (%)	8.11	5.60	
<i>Variety</i>			
Kanak	5.3	5.4	5.3
Ratna	4.5	4.8	4.6
IR64	4.6	4.8	4.7
CD (P = 0.05)	0.21	0.25	
CV (%)	5.16	6.22	

yield of 5.4 t ha⁻¹ at 120 kg N ha⁻¹. Among the varieties, Kanak was again first (Table 3). Kanak is a mid-early duration variety that grows in 125–130 d under transplanted conditions. It is a dwarf variety with very good early plant vigor. Its 1,000-grain weight is 24.31 g. The kernels are long, slender, white, and translucent. The variety is resistant to neck blast and is moderately resistant to brown spot, leaf blast, and sheath rot.

Table 3. Effect of different N levels on grain yield of rice varieties.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Mean
	1999	2000	
<i>N level (kg ha⁻¹)</i>			
0	3.3	3.4	3.3
30	3.8	4.0	3.9
60	4.6	4.7	4.7
90	5.0	5.1	5.0
120	5.4	5.5	5.4
CD (P = 0.05)	0.22	0.27	
CV (%)	5.46	4.15	
<i>Variety</i>			
Kanak	5.4	5.5	5.5
Ratna	4.4	4.6	4.5
IR64	4.5	4.6	4.6
CD (P = 0.05)	0.19	0.18	
CV (%)		8.11	6.25

Vasumati—a new Basmati variety released in India

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India, the home of the long-grained aromatic rice Basmati, has established a monopoly in exporting basmati rice, which fetches a price two to three times higher than that of regular rice. The country earns as much as Rs 18 billion annually in foreign exchange. Although several aromatic

rice varieties are grown and consumed as basmati, only a few types, such as Basmati 370, Type 3, Taroari Basmati, and Pakistani Basmati, are considered economically important as they possess the quality features required of exported rice (IARI 1980). The traditional basmati varieties are tall,

low-yielding, and susceptible to a range of pests and diseases. Efforts to develop short-statured, nonlodging, high-yielding basmati varieties, insulated with pest and disease resistance and possessing distinct quality features, resulted in the release of Kasturi, Pusa Basmati 1, and other varieties

ies in the early 1990s (Shobha Rani 1992). This was followed by several other varieties. But many of these varieties had few basmati characteristics. With the rise in exports of basmati from India since the 1990s, varietal improvement efforts received further impetus. Through coordinated efforts, 10 elite lines were identified, including IET15391 (RP3135-17-12-8-8)—released by the Central SubCommittee on Crop Standards, Notification and Release of Varieties, a national body—as Vasumati for traditional basmati-growing areas of northwestern India.

Overall, Vasumati recorded a mean grain yield of 4.1, 4.3, 3.3, and 3.7 t ha⁻¹ in 1996, 1997, 1998, and 2000, respectively, establishing a significant yield superiority of 12.4% over the best check Pusa Basmati 1 and 46.9% over Taroari Basmati, a traditional export-quality check (Table 1). In 17 out of 19 trials pooled over years in the states of Haryana, Punjab, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu, and Kashmir, and Rajasthan, it was at the top and was superior to checks Taroari Basmati and Pusa Basmati 1 in 11 and 9 trials, respectively.

Vasumati is a semidwarf (110 cm), compact, and non-lodging ideotype that matures in 135 d. In addition to its long slender, highly aromatic, and translucent grains, Vasumati is endowed with all the unique quality fea-

tures of basmati varieties (Table 2). It has intermediate amylose content (25.2%) and alkali value (4.2, 4.1). It recorded excellent linear elongation with a desirable slender, flaky texture upon cooking, which is on a par with checks Taroari Basmati and Pusa Basmati 1. In panel tests where appearance, cohesiveness, tenderness on touching, chewing, taste, aroma, and elongation were scored, Vasumati achieved consistently high ratings and was on a par with standard checks (see figure). In addition, Vasumati possesses moderate resistance to leaf blast and brown spot, high resistance to gall midge biotypes 1 and 4, and moderate resistance to whitebacked planthopper. With its resistance to /tolerance for major pests, Vasumati can be pro-

duced pesticide- and residue-free for export and can replace traditional and evolved varieties in Punjab, Haryana, Uttaranchal, Jammu and Kashmir, Himachal Pradesh, Western Uttar Pradesh, and Rajasthan because of its unique basmati quality traits and higher yield advantage.

References

- IARI (Indian Agricultural Research Institute). 1980. High-yielding basmati rice—problems, progress and prospects. Res. Bull. 30. 47 p.
- Shobha Rani N. 1992. Research efforts to develop scented quality rices for increased productivity and export purposes. Paper presented at the seminar for the “Awardees of Outstanding Young Women in Rice Science.” International Rice Research Conference, 21-25 Apr 1992, International Rice Research Institute, Los Baños, Philippines.

Table 2. Grain quality characteristics^a of Vasumati.

Characteristic	Vasumati	Taroari Basmati	Pusa Basmati I
Milling (%)	69.7	67.1	65.3
Head rice recovery (%)	55.3	45.9	54.6
Kernel length (mm)	7.23	7.30	7.34
Length/breadth	3.96	4.04	4.11
Kernel length after cooking (mm)	13.5	14.3	14.4
Elongation ratio	1.86	1.95	1.98
Alkali value ^b	4.2, 4.1	5.4, 5.3	7.0, 7.0
Amylose content (%)	25.19	23.15	23.93
Water uptake (mL)	157	202	302
Volume expansion ratio	4.2	4.3	4.4
Aroma	Strongly scented	Strongly scented	Strongly scented

^aAnalyzed at the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad. ^bAlkali values measured in a scale of 1–7.

Table 1. Yield performance of Vasumati (IET15391) in traditional basmati-growing areas.

Year of testing	Trials (no.)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
		IET15391	Taroari Basmati	Pusa Basmati I
1996	2	4.1	3.2	3.4
1997	4	4.3	2.9	4.1
1998	6	3.3	1.8	2.8
2000	7	3.7	2.7	3.6
Overall mean	19	3.9	2.6	3.5

Rough rice and cooked rice of Vasumati (left) compared with traditional check Taroari Basmati (right).